

FARCLIMATE

DELIVERABLE D2.3

Stakeholder Management Strategy

Due date of submission: 30/06/2024

Actual submission date: 31/07/2024

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List of acronyms

GTA: Gender Transformative Approach

D: Deliverable

DVF: Desirability, Viability, Feasibility Framework

EC: European Commission

EU: European Union

IPCC: Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

MIP4Adapt: EU Mission Implementation Platform

NGO: Non-Governmental Organisation

RAST: Regional Adaptation Support Tool

REWAISE: REsilient WATER Innovation for Smart Economy Project

R&D: Research and Development

T: Task

SISCODE: Society in Innovation and Science through CODEsign Project

SME: Small and Medium Enterprise

SWOT: Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats

UN: United Nations

UNALAB: Urban Nature Labs Project

URBANOME: URBAN Observatory for Multi-participatory Enhancement of health and wellbeing Project

WP: Work Package

Project information

Project full title: Moving ForwARd to achieving CLIMATE-resilient and sustainable European regional economic systems - FARCLIMATE

Acronym: FARCLIMATE

Call: HORIZON-MISS-2022-CLIMA-01

Topic: HORIZON-MISS-2022-CLIMA-01-04 - Transformation of regional economic systems for climate resilience and sustainability

Start date: 1st October 2023

Duration: 48 months

List of participants:

Partner No.	Organisation Name Acronym
1 (Coord.)	UNIVERSIDAD DE VIGO UVIGO
2	CONTACTICA S.L. CTA
3	INTERNATIONAL UNION FOR CONSERVATION OF NATURE IUCN
4	C4G - CONSULTING AND TRAINING NETWORK, LDA C4G
5	INVIALE LIFE CYCLE THINKING S.L. INV
6	MUNICIPIO DO FUNDAO FUNDAO
7	GREEN GROWTH GENERATION GGG
8	UNIVERSITY OF LIEGE ULIEGE
9	FUNDACIÓN CENTRO DE SERVICIOS Y PROMOCIÓN FORESTAL Y DE SU INDUSTRIA DE CASTILLA Y LEÓN CESEFOR
10	UNIVERSIDADE NOVA DE LISBOA UNL
11	FUNDACIÓN PARA LA PESCA Y MARISQUEO FUNDAMAR FUNDAMAR
12	EUROPEAN NETWORK OF LIVING LABS IVZW ENoLL
13	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS CERTH
14	LAUREA-AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY LAU

Deliverable details

Document Number:	D2.3
Document Title:	Stakeholder Management Strategy
Dissemination level	PU – Public
Period:	PR1
WP:	WP2
Task:	T2.3
Author:	Juan Freire (INV), Beatriz Rivela (INV)
Abstract:	<p>This document focuses on the development of a comprehensive Stakeholder Management Strategy for the FARCLIMATE project, emphasizing co-creation with a multi-actor, gender-balanced, and inclusive approach. This strategy builds upon a preliminary stakeholder analysis that identified and categorized key stakeholders, including regional and local government policymakers, private sector entities (particularly SMEs), business associations, labour unions, consumer and civil society organizations, academia, research and technology centres, NGOs, and professionals and experts across the value chains of agriculture, fishery, and forestry. The strategy is designed to facilitate stakeholder engagement tailored to the unique needs and contributions of each group, guided by insights from the final selection of case studies (T2.2) and evaluated through the Living Lab User Persona framework. It also aligns closely with T8.1, the Communication and Dissemination Strategy, ensuring effective engagement of stakeholders based on their interests, responsibilities, and potential contributions to the FARCLIMATE project.</p>

Version	Date	Description
Draft_V0	21/07/2024	First draft
Draft_V1	25/07/2024	Second draft
Version_V1	26/07/2024	Initial version
Version_V2	29/07/2024	Second version

1 Executive Summary

The present document, developed in Task T2.3 as part of WP2 "Case Studies Development and Stakeholder Interaction" of the FARCLIMATE project, synthesises a **Stakeholder Management Strategy** that serves as a **blueprint** to ensure the **engagement of different stakeholders** according to their interests, responsibilities, positions, and potential contributions in the development of the various case studies as living labs. The strategy is informed by the **Methodological Approach for FARCLIMATE** (D2.1) as well as the **compilation of FARCLIMATE case studies** (D2.2) and is complemented by the guidelines described in the **Gender Transformative Approach** (D1.5) and the **Communication and Dissemination Plan** (D8.1) of the project.

Firstly, **Section 2** places the case studies and living labs, the backbone of the methodology in the FARCLIMATE project, in the **context of the frameworks of participatory approaches to innovation** and the characteristics of **challenges** and **problems** where these approaches are essential. Stakeholder management here is focused on generating **effective engagement** to ensure that the diversity of experiences, expertise, and knowledge needed in effective user-driven living labs is adequately represented. Finally, the **specifics of FARCLIMATE**, particularly its large-scale approach (20 case studies with approximately 600 stakeholders involved, most with little to no prior experience), are used to justify the approach followed in the definition of a Stakeholder Management Strategy as a detailed blueprint for Case Study development in a Living Lab process.

Building on these conditions, **Section 3** dives into the **general methodological approach** for developing this strategy. **Section 4** then explores the **integrative and complementary processes** of Living Labs, highlighting their temporal sequences and interdependencies. Together, these sections form the blueprint's foundation. Moving forward, **Section 5** brings the **Mapping Canvas** into focus. This essential strategic tool serves as the template for setting up and developing the Living Labs.

We propose a journey that explicitly connects and coordinates the different phases and actions of the integrative and complementary processes for Living Labs. This **journey** is outlined at a high level in **Section 6** and in detail in **Section 7**, including a timeline that serves as a flexible template, adaptable to the unique circumstances of each case study.

Finally, **Section 8** offers a **catalogue of tools** with recommendations for their application in each activity of the Living Labs' development. It identifies the stakeholders involved, both leading and participating, and some recommendations to get the best use and performance of the tools.

The **Annexes** include **additional resources** to support the implementation of various activities required for developing Living Labs. **Annex 1** synthesizes the **key concepts** and **terminology** for stakeholder management in climate adaptation, while **Annex 2** presents **references** for further reading and detailed descriptions of specific methods related to the **definition** of the **stakeholder management strategy**. **Tools** and **recommendations** for stakeholder **mapping** and effective management are described in **Annex 3**. Finally, **Annex 4** showcases the high-level and detailed views of the **Case Study Journey**, as well as the **toolbox** for stakeholder management.

2 Introduction

2.1 The need for participatory approaches to innovation

FARCLIMATE focuses on **climate adaptation** by empowering local communities to ensure just and inclusive transitions. In this context, **Living Labs** have been chosen as the appropriate **strategic methodological framework**. Living Labs represent a collection of innovation frameworks based on co-creation by a diverse ecosystem of stakeholders. Co-creation here is understood as a sequence of four phases: **Discover, Define, Develop, and Deliver**. This process is sometimes referred to as the **Double Diamond framework** (Fig. 1), popularised in recent decades by design organisations such as IDEO and the UK Design Council (Design Council, 2015).

Figure 1. The Double Diamond innovation framework as proposed by the UK Design Council, highlighting the key role of stakeholder engagement in the process. Source: Design Council (2015).

We should initially ask ourselves why this approach is the right one for the challenges we face in the present project. Specifically, two key questions are relevant: **What type of diversity and participatory processes are important in innovation related to territorial climate adaptation?** And **why do we need lab formats to generate this kind of innovation?**

We must keep in mind the **wide diversity of innovation approaches**. In 2018, Nesta, the UK's innovation agency for social good, published the first version of a mapping exercise on innovation methods and approaches, based on participant observation of innovation practices across various contexts (Leurs, 2018). A significant and central area of this landscape (Fig. 2), featuring **Living Labs** prominently, is occupied by a range of approaches that share a common need for stakeholder diversity and types of engagement. This area, representing the diversity of participatory approaches, includes different “spaces” essential for driving change:

- **Intelligence** to make sense of and conceptualise reality.
- **Solutions** to test and develop solutions.
- **Technology** to enable action and change.
- **Talent** to mobilise skills, develop capabilities, and enhance organisational readiness to ultimately drive happen.

Figure 2. Landscape of innovation approaches mapped by Nesta. Source: Leurs (2018).

2.1.1 Wicked problems require experts in experience

The main reason participatory approaches are important in innovation is that they are especially well suited to address **wicked problems** (Rittel & Webber, 1973; Conklin, 2006). In the 1970s, the term “wicked problem” was coined to describe a type of **complex problem** that is difficult or impossible to solve because **it cannot be**

fully defined, is **multi-causal**, and any **solution** is inherently **partial** due to changing conditions and potential negative impacts. Most of the critical problems nowadays for our society could be defined as wicked, and those related to the climate crisis are a clear and canonical example. These types of problems pose methodological challenges since, as they are not completely defined, they can only be understood through immersion and, therefore, only when they affect us because we are an active part of the process itself. **Experts and planners** address well-defined problems through diagnoses based on “**professional**” **knowledge**. Complex and chronic problems need listening and a diversity of points of view and epistemologies.

Understanding different perspectives and angles of a context requires **diversity** in the participating voices. This diversity extends beyond professional knowledge, and multi- or interdisciplinarity alone is not enough. We need the voices of citizens and practitioners who are directly affected and, in this sense, are “**experts in experience**”. These individuals build the perception and definition of the problem alongside experts and those responsible for managing it.

Experts in experience are those individuals and groups who **have experienced firsthand** a health condition, a specific disease, dispossession, a climate crisis, abuse of power, discrimination, etc. They possess deep knowledge of the **symptoms** and **consequences** of their situation, as well as familiarity with the daily **challenges**, unmet **needs**, and **barriers** to treatment and care (Rabeharisoa & Callon, 2002).

To discover and develop effective solutions for complex problems, we must incorporate both agents with certified expertise and those whose knowledge is based on personal experience. Sultana et al. (2024) provides a recent example of the need to involve local communities to achieve effective and just climate adaptation. In this case, the study relates to safe water access and highlights how crucial it is for local communities to be involved.

2.1.2 The emergence of Innovation Labs

Different professional practices and academic approaches have proposed and tested **methodological frameworks** to develop **effective participatory innovation**, such as **user-centred innovation** (popularised as the central process of design thinking), **user-driven innovation** (Gambardella et al., 2017; Von Hippel, 2005, 2016), and **citizen innovation** (Gómez-Abad & Freire, 2023; Lafuente, 2023; Pascale & Resina, 2020). These different approaches share attributes but also differ in the role and empowerment given to the various participants and the degree of leadership exercised by the different types of experts.

To facilitate and drive these types of innovation, several innovation **lab formats** have emerged. These labs should be seen as **infrastructures** and **organisational forms** designed to encourage citizen and stakeholder participation and the creation of innovative solutions that help address and better understand complex problems (Gómez-Abad & Freire, 2023).

In parallel with the different approaches mentioned earlier, these labs represent a **spectrum of participant roles and the prominence of experts**, ranging from R&D Labs led by professional experts to Design Labs where experience experts engage in co-creation under the methodological guidance of professional designers, or Citizen Labs where diverse stakeholders collaborate without predetermined epistemological hierarchies. In this context, over the past decades, **Living Labs** have developed multiple approaches to adapt to four types of innovation drivers: **utilizer-driven, enabler-driven, provider-driven, and user-driven**. Thus, Living Labs can be considered a **flexible framework** for adapting participatory innovation to specific goals related to objectives and processes.

2.1.3 The methodological approach of FARCLIMATE

In the FARCLIMATE project, **user-driven Living Labs** have been selected to generate truly just and inclusive approaches to solving a range of genuine wicked problems related to climate change adaptation in various territories and communities. In this sense, the Living Labs to be developed in FARCLIMATE are closer to Citizen Labs than traditional R&D Labs.

In summary, to address wicked problems, we need **inclusive** and **situated approaches** that involve a diverse range of participants, including those who live and experience the problem in the territory. This approach should facilitate productive dialogue among multiple epistemologies with minimal or weak a priori hierarchies among stakeholders. To achieve these goals, we must expand and adapt our innovation toolbox to successfully tackle emerging tasks such as:

- **Discovery** through immersion and active participation.
- **Mediation** to support effective communication and collaboration among diverse stakeholders, addressing their diversity of needs, desires, and potential pains.
- **Continuous experimentation and prototyping** to generate valuable knowledge for the territory and local communities, involving action-based research and ongoing learning.

2.2 The importance of effective stakeholder engagement in climate adaptation

Strong evidence suggests that **public participation** can lead to more ambitious and **transformative climate change planning and implementation**. The benefits of public participation include increased legitimacy, justice, and equity in planning processes and outcomes; heightened community awareness and empowerment; greater willingness for cooperation and dialogue; and enhanced individual behavioural change. These factors contribute to stronger, more resilient communities (Ensor et al., 2018; Campos et al., 2016). Given the urgent need for societal transformation in response to the climate crisis (IPCC, 2018; 2013), public participation is increasingly seen as **crucial** for **achieving climate resilience** and carbon neutrality through local and regional decision-making.

Cattino and Reckien's (2021) review of scientific literature on climate adaptation reveals that public participation has a **positive impact** on both **mitigation** and **adaptation**. Their findings indicate that the public has much higher ambition for adaptation and a slightly higher ambition for mitigation than the people with decision-making power. The influence of participation on adaptation is stronger than the influence on mitigation. The review highlights four key conditions for public participation to drive transformative action and elevate local climate ambition: 1) recognizing all actors, 2) ensuring their clear and meaningful involvement throughout all decision-making stages, 3) granting full decision-making power to the involved public, and 4) supporting a welfare-oriented logic rather than focusing solely on safety (or prioritising social over human security).

In the European context, the EU Mission Implementation Platform for Adaptation to Climate Change launched the **DIY Manual for Stakeholder and Citizen Engagement in Climate Change Adaptation** (MIP4Adapt, 2023) for use by **regional and local authorities**. The manual provides a guide on how to engage stakeholders and citizens throughout the six main steps of the climate change adaptation planning process described in the **Regional Adaptation Support Tool (RAST)** (Bilgram et al., 2024), presenting tried and tested tools and methods to support a “whole-of-society” approach that leaves no one behind. The manual is conceptually underpinned by four elements: communicate, engage, connect, and enable (action). It emphasises the crucial role that regional and local authorities can play in building or enhancing stakeholders' and citizens' awareness and understanding of climate vulnerabilities, risks, and opportunities, and in strengthening their commitment to

addressing these issues. This, in turn, can facilitate implementation and promote behavioural change (see Box 1).

Why do you need to engage and mobilise stakeholders and citizens?

By engaging your stakeholders and citizens, you can ensure that your climate change adaptation plans are:

Salient: While much may be known about the sensitivity of human and natural systems to climate variability and change, stakeholders and citizens can provide important local insights, knowledge, and experience. Furthermore, they may be the best judge of their own adaptive capacity; their ability to adjust to potential damages, to take advantage of opportunities, or to respond to consequences. Many stakeholders are also likely to be responsible for implementing actions arising from the plan, so they will likely be knowledgeable about operational issues and deployment.

Credible: If your climate change adaptation plan is to be credible, consistent, and trustworthy, then it is important that it is informed bottom-up not just led top-down.

Legitimate: By securing inputs to and validation of your climate change adaptation plan from stakeholders and citizens, it is more likely to be seen as fair, proportionate, and equitable by all, thereby facilitating your ability to ensure its implementation.

Jointly owned: Co-development of your plan with stakeholders and citizens will ensure common ownership and encourage everyone to play their part in its implementation.

Understood: The involvement of stakeholders and citizens in each step of the adaptation planning cycle (e.g., in defining climate vulnerabilities and risks, identifying and prioritising adaptation options, and developing implementation plans) will mean that the purposes of the plan, the issues on which it focuses and the ways in which these are addressed will be familiar, better known and thus understood.

Box 1. Why do you need to engage and mobilise stakeholders and citizens? Source: DIY Manual for Stakeholder and Citizen Engagement in Climate Change Adaptation (MIP4Adapt, 2023).

The approach to stakeholder management in FARCLIMATE is informed by the **guidelines of MIP4Adapt** and takes a **conceptual leap** by placing people at the centre of the innovation process. This is aligned with the **Methodological Approach of FARCLIMATE** (see D2.1), which establishes that stakeholders are key to the Living Lab approach (Bódi et al., 2022; ENOLL 2010). Living Labs place citizens at the heart of the innovation process and facilitate joint-value co-creation, rapid prototyping, and the scaling up of innovations and businesses. A Living Lab operates within real-life settings and adopts a user-centric approach, being flexible in its deployment according to purpose, scope, objectives, duration, actor involvement, participation levels, and boundaries (Bódi et al., 2022).

In the conceptual framework of the FARCLIMATE project, stakeholder management refers to the combination of actions and strategies designed to engage a diverse ecosystem of stakeholders within the Living Lab context, according to the selected user-driven innovation framework. We define **stakeholders** broadly as "all parties who will be affected by or will affect [the project's] strategy" (Nutt and Backoff, 1992). Given that the project focuses on territories and inclusive approaches, local communities are of critical relevance as stakeholders. In this sense, each living lab aims to create and dynamize a community of innovation, understood as a community of practice and practitioners (Wenger, 1998).

Following the methods of the European Network of Living Labs (ENOLL), the general strategy for stakeholder management in Living Labs should include the following tasks:

- Identify and **map the key stakeholders** of the **quadruple helix** (public sector, academia, business, and citizens) who should be involved in the living lab activities.
- Analyse the **level of interest and power of influence** of each stakeholder using the power vs. interest matrix. This analysis will help prioritise stakeholders who should be more deeply involved.
- Establish a **clear governance model** that defines the roles, responsibilities, and decision-making processes to facilitate coordination and co-creation among the various stakeholders.
- Foster the **active participation of end-users** throughout the entire innovation lifecycle, ensuring that their needs and feedback are captured and integrated.
- Develop an **effective communication strategy** to share knowledge, best practices, and lessons learned with the community, promoting transparency and openness within the Living Lab.
- Continuously **monitor and evaluate the impact** of Living Lab activities, making adjustments to stakeholder engagement strategies as needed.

In essence, the overall goal is to involve all key stakeholders in a balanced manner, fostering co-creation and transparency throughout the process.

2.3 Background and context of stakeholder management within the FARCLIMATE Project

Task **T2.2** of **WP2** of the FARCLIMATE project, "**Case Studies Development and Stakeholders Interaction**", focuses on **selecting case studies** to set up and develop in the Living Lab format. Within the scope of this task, the declaration of intentions that FARCLIMATE partners communicate to individuals and organisations potentially interested in becoming part of a case study establishes the following:

[Living Labs are] understood as open innovation ecosystems in which different stakeholders work together to co-create solutions to relevant problems in their community, from products and services to policies and business models. Living labs focus on co-developing, rapid prototyping, testing and scaling up solutions. They operate in real-life settings and involve active user participation to validate solutions and get closer to their adoption. Living labs act as intermediaries and orchestrators, involving citizens, research institutions, public administrations and businesses in the open innovation ecosystem. Living labs offer several benefits to regions and local communities.

...

[And the] mission in FARCLIMATE is to help case studies launch a successful living lab in their local community and gain the skills to develop local solutions for climate change adaptation. To do that, we will help case study teams engage stakeholders, develop living lab capabilities..., and implement the first local projects in the agriculture, silviculture or fishing sectors.

To accomplish this task, a **general methodology for Living Labs** has been defined in **Task T2.1** (this methodological approach is documented in **D2.1**), considering the general process and the main tools available. The Living Lab framework allows to generate innovation based on participatory processes where diverse stakeholders engage in the three “spaces”: understanding the problems and challenges (problem), ideation and active research to identify potential solutions (solution), and experimental implementation of those solutions to gather evidence and insights, enabling the scaling and transfer of proven solutions (deployment.)

Figure 3. General diagram of the flow of tasks in WP2 and their connection with the main Living Lab phases.

Task 2.3 focuses on the design of the stakeholder management strategy, which is described in this document. Figure 3 shows the **general diagram of the flow of tasks in WP2** and their connection with the main Living Lab phases. It should be noted that although case study selection and methodology deployment are macro-processes occurring in parallel at a high level, they should be, and are in fact, coordinated and interact with each other.

This strategy is complemented by the **Gender Transformative Approach (GTA)** of FARCLIMATE, which aims to ensure that all project activities promote gender transformation. This includes understanding and challenging gender norms, ensuring equitable access and control, involving all genders in decision-making, and monitoring progress throughout implementation. The GTA, described in **D1.5**, constitutes a **living document** that will undergo a continuous process of interaction and exchange during the project's implementation. Additionally, the work developed in Task **T8.1**, "**Communication and Dissemination Strategy**" -specifically the **Communication and Dissemination Plan** detailed in **D8.1** -contributes to ensuring the engagement of different stakeholders according to their interests, responsibilities, positions, and potential contributions.

2.4 Purpose and objectives of the FARCLIMATE Stakeholder Management Strategy

Developing FARCLIMATE case studies requires establishing a Living Lab from the ground up and at a large scale, aiming to engage at least 600 stakeholders across 20 regions through the established Living Labs. In most cases, this process will be led by individuals and organisations that may not have prior experience with Living Labs or similar innovation frameworks and will need to start from scratch to achieve a sophisticated result (an operational Living Lab). Although experts will accompany the process, a blueprint for the Living Lab setup and deployment, which essentially materialises the stakeholder management strategy, will be critical to guide the process and empower participants.

The general **goal** of the **Stakeholder Management Strategy** is to make a **deep dive** into the **Living Labs methods** related to stakeholder management; **enrich the toolbox** with adjacent methods taken from nearby participatory innovation approaches such as those derived from different design practices, user-lead innovation, or the citizen labs approaches previously discussed; and provide a **detailed blueprint** that adapts the general methodology to a process specific for FARCLIMATE case studies.

In summary, this document addresses these three main objectives of the Stakeholder Management Strategy:

1. Provide a **general journey for the setup, deployment and operation** of a Living Lab that integrates the different processes: the central "integrative process" along with the training, communication, evaluation and construction of the Living Lab canvas. The canvas will be developed progressively as deployment advances, stakeholders become involved, and evidence is gathered.
2. A **stakeholder management and engagement toolbox**, which is a collection of tools that can be utilised in various activities during the Living Lab setup and deployment. Each tool is categorised based on the processes in which it can be used. Most of the tools have been proposed or identified by ENOLL in D2.1 and other documents, while some additional complementary tools, drawn from participatory innovation approaches close to the Living Labs framework (such as citizen labs), have been added. Various tools could be used in an integrated and flexible manner for a given activity. The toolbox is an open catalogue that should be updated and expanded to include new tools and uses based on suggestions by experts and users, as well as experience gained during the project.
3. **Blueprint for the Living Lab setup, deployment, and operation**, providing a detailed plan for setting up, deploying, and operating a Living Lab. It outlines a series of activities that have been selected and adapted for the development of the case studies of the FARCLIMATE project in a Living Lab format.

3 Methodological Approach: A Detailed Blueprint for Case Study Development

As we previously introduced, the methodology proposed here is **based on**, **deepens**, and **structures** the **Methodological Approach of WP2** (D2.1) within a **broader conceptual framework** and follows the **guidelines** of the **EU Climate Adaptation Mission** (MIP4Adapt, 2023), including aspects promoting **gender** transformation and **inclusion**. On the other hand, this document of the strategy should be considered **Version 1**, designed to **help** and **guide** the **setup** and **deployment** of the **first group of Living Labs**. Throughout the FARCLIMATE project, experience and insights will be incorporated into future versions of this strategy and derived documents and publications. In this sense, the setup and development of case studies and Living Labs will occur in two batches. The first batch, in **autumn 2024**, will test, validate, and improve this blueprint to implement the learnings in the second phase starting in 2025.

The definition of the stakeholder management strategy is addressed by designing a **blueprint** for the Living Lab Setup, Deployment, and Operation specifically adapted to FARCLIMATE case studies. The **design exercise** is structured in the **following phases**, which are detailed in the subsequent sections of this report:

- A. Define the **flow and connections** of the **integrative** and **complementary** processes of Living Labs.
- B. Adapt the **Living Lab Mapping Canvas** as **template** for Living Labs **setup** and **development**.
- C. Integrate the **Living Lab processes** and **phases** in a detailed **Case Study Journey**.
- D. Design a **general Case Study Journey** for the setup of Living Labs.
- E. Develop a **toolbox** for stakeholder engagement.

Since one of the main goals in FARCLIMATE is to develop each case study in a Living Lab format, it is important to understand the **general journey** of this process. This journey, in simple terms, outlines the timing and sequence of actions, the connections and dependencies among them, and the main types of stakeholders involved (at a high level: project partners, local core team, other local stakeholders). Actions define **touchpoints** where different stakeholders interact with a definite goal and produce some result (whether a piece of knowledge or a decision).

In this way, the **blueprint** will provide a **detailed plan** for setting up, deploying, and operating a Living Lab. Finally, it proposes a series of activities needed to develop each case study in a Living Lab format, with each activity representing a touchpoint with stakeholders characterised by:

- A clearly defined objective.
- A suggested main tool (from the toolbox).
- Other relevant resources (also from the toolbox).
- The participants (using the categories of stakeholders and general roles in Living Labs).
- A detailed description.

Additionally, the blueprint suggests durations and timing for each activity (in weeks), serving as a calendar template to guide the setup and deployment process. Naturally, each case study has its own circumstances, and the process and timing should be adapted. The experience gained should enable us to develop an evidence-based blueprint by the end of the project.

4 Integrative and Complementary Processes of Living Lab

The primary reference to design the journey is the **main integrative process** governing the Living Lab (Fig. 4). This process is described in detail in D2.1 and is based in Mastelic (2019). In brief, this process is grounded in

the frameworks and practices of **design thinking** and **strategic design**, and defines the main phases: problem understanding, ideation of solutions, prototyping, experimentation and scaling up. Each phase includes a sequence of divergence and convergence according to the double diamond model, which represents the standard for user-driven innovation.

Figure 4. Main integrative process of Living Labs as described in detail in D2.1, adapted from Mastelic (2019).

The Living Lab methodology defines **other processes**, such as Living Lab Mapping Canvas, Training, Evaluation and Communication, that are **complementary** and reinforce the main one, developing the needed capabilities and assuring the focus. In the following sections the activities related to stakeholder management will be defined for each process (main and complimentary) providing tools and insights about timing and context.

5 Living Lab Mapping Canvas as a Template for Living Lab Set Up and Development

The **Living Lab Mapping Canvas** developed by ENOLL is perhaps the most relevant **strategic tool** and it is recommended here as a **template** for Living Lab set up and development. The origin, objectives and utilities of this canvas is explained in detail in D2.1, and especially in the following paragraph see Section 5.1 of D2.1 for detailed information):

The Living Lab Mapping Canvas, developed by ENOLL, serves as a tool to outline the key components of Living Labs, aiding in understanding their level of maturity. Initially crafted in 2019 as part of the EU-funded URBANOME project¹. This canvas has since been customised for various areas of work. The canvas [...] has been specifically tailor to FARCLIMATE project and the Case Studies. This chapter introduces the Mapping Canvas, followed by suggested workshops to populate its sections. The Can-

¹ <https://www.urbanome.eu/>

vas is also aligned with the Living Lab three-layer model classification approach [...] As the FARCLIMATE project aims to develop certifiable Living Labs, the Canvas has been modified to target the Macro level development. In particular, yellow quadrants are essential for establishing a Living Lab at a Macro level, and orange quadrants applicable across all levels: Macro, Meso, and Micro.

Here, we propose using the Living Lab Mapping Canvas to promote stakeholder engagement in the following way. The different components of the canvas will be defined sequentially as **exercises** occurring along the **Living Lab journey** to **reflect** and **make decisions** about the objectives (**why**), the methods (**what**) and the resources / governance (**how**). Instead of conceiving the definition of the canvas at a specific, early moment of the journey, the **sequential / progressive approach** allows to a) define each component more robustly using the evidence and experience gathered up to that point; b) use these moments and activities to reflect about the process and consolidate the learnings; and c) favour a participatory approach in the decisions about the strategic aspects tackled by the canvas.

Instead, if the canvas were defined (only) in the initial phases, most of the decisions would be mere hypotheses, possibilities, and speculations, with the leading team having an excessive influence on the decisions and outcomes. On the other hand, the initial effort to gather information in the preliminary startup stages of the Living Lab, where the characterization of some analysis elements is still speculative, can be overwhelming and discourage the participation of actors without prior experience in this type of participatory process.

Figure 5. Desirability, Viability, Feasibility (DVF) Framework from IDEO used here to organise temporally the Living Lab Mapping Canvas. Taken from: <https://makeiterate.com/ideos-desirability-viability-feasibility-framework-a-practical-guide/>.

To implement this sequential approach the **components** of the canvas are treated as **activities**, ordered over **time**, and **connected** with **other activities** along the journey. The **leaders** and main participants (FARCLIMATE Partners; Core team of case study; Stakeholder) for developing each component are also established.

For ordering the components, we follow the **Desirability, Viability, Feasibility (DVF) Framework** from IDEO (Fig. 5), a foundational company in the field of design thinking and a key player in defining and disseminating

the different methodologies and frameworks used today in design approaches to innovation. This framework is a product **prioritisation method** that helps teams evaluate three key aspects of a successful product: desirability, viability and feasibility.

In our case, we propose to group the different components of the canvas into three categories corresponding to the three key aspects of the DVF framework and to execute them in the following general sequence:

Desirability -> Feasibility -> Viability (Sustainability)

Figure 6. Adaptation of the Living Lab (LL) Mapping Canvas (Bódi et al., 2022). One-sided arrow implies a sequence; two-sided arrows indicate parallel activities.

Figure 6 shows the proposed **adaptation of the Living Lab Mapping Canvas**, assigning each component to one of the main categories of the DVF Framework and including a proposed sequence for defining each component throughout the Living Lab development for FARCLIMATE Case Studies. Each activity related to the canvas, which involves defining each component, should be completed in the following order, with some components

addressed in parallel (two-sided arrows indicate parallel activities in Fig. 6), as will be explained in detail in the following sections:

- DESIRABILITY:** 1. Purpose -> 2. Vision and scope -> 3. Living Lab context -> 4. Host organisation(s) | 1, 2 and 3 are parallel activities.
- FEASIBILITY:** 5. Overview of all stakeholders -> 6. Stakeholders and external roles -> 7. People and internal roles -> 8. Communication strategy & Channels -> 9. Monitoring & Evaluation -> 10. Strategy. 5 bold steps exercise -> 11. SWOT | 6 and 7 are parallel activities.
- VIABILITY:** 12. Governance -> 13. Value for stakeholders -> 14. Resources & Sustainability | 12 and 13 are parallel activities.

6 Integration of Living Lab Processes and Phases in a Detailed Case Study Journey

In this section we present the **detailed version** of the **Case Study Journey**, explicitly connecting and coordinating in time the different phases and actions of the integrative and complementary processes for Living Labs. The timeline is presented indicating the temporal scale (months in which the action takes place and duration), as a referential template that could and should be adapted to the specific circumstances of each case study.

The Journey is provided in two formats:

1. A **high-level view of the Case Study Journey**, organised along the phases of the integrative process for Living Labs, including the temporal coordination with actions related to the complementary processes. The purpose of the high-level view is to help **understand the complete process** and the connections among different phases.
2. A **detailed view of the Case Study Journey**, where each touchpoint is mapped with a colour code corresponding to the phases of the integrative and complementary processes. The purpose of the detailed view is to serve as a manual to **guide the sequence of activities** that need to be developed and the characteristics of each activity.

Screenshots of the **high-level** and **detailed views** of the Case Study Journey are summarised in **Figures 7 and 8**, respectively. In **Annex 4**, a link to the original spreadsheet tables is included, allowing users to delve deeper into the contents and modify and adapt the tool to their specific case. Additionally, a higher resolution version of the high-level view and the detailed view, including all information fields (resources and participants), is provided.

PROCESSES		Problem space			Solution space			Deployment space	
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Living Lab Integrative Process		EMPATHISE: Select a practice	EMPATHISE: Integrate Stakeholders	DEFINE: Uncover barriers	IDEATE: Co-design plan	PROTOTYPE: Pilot an intervention	TEST: Evaluate performance	IMPLEMENT: Demonstrate the system	SCALE UP: Exploit the solution
Selection and activation of case studies		Mapping problems and territories		Negotiation with core teams					
Living Lab Mapping Canvas		Desirability 3, 4		Feasibility 1, 2		Viability 5, 6, 7, 8, 9			10, 11
Trainings		Introductory sessions (partners)		Introductory sessions (stakeholders)			Living Lab Crash Course		
Evaluation					Cycle 1		Cycle 2		Cycle 3
Communication									
Time (months)		0-2	3-4	5-6	<1	7-12	<1	13-	
Duration (months)		2	2	2	<1	5	<1		

Figure 7. High-level view of the Case Study Journey. Time 0 refers to the formal kick-off of the Living Lab (after negotiation and agreements with the core team).

The detailed journey, designed in alignment with the integrative processes of Living Labs, includes the **Mapping Canvas** as a **sequence of activities guiding the Living Lab development** and incorporates activities related to other complementary processes (Trainings, Evaluation, and Communication). In synthesis, the journey is composed of a sequence of **touchpoints**, each characterised by the following information:

(sequence) and time (week #). Touchpoints are ordered along the journey (although in some cases there could be overlaps) and for each one, a proposed duration is provided (in weeks). The start and end weeks are indicated, considering time 0 as a co-creation workshop where the components of the Canvas related to Desirability (see DVF framework) are defined. Some activities, which formally occur before the setup of the case study, are indicated with negative times.

Touchpoint. The action that involves an interaction among some (or all) the different stakeholders (partners, core team, other local stakeholders) with a specific objective, generating some form of knowledge (e.g., a map, document, artefact, etc. and/or decision).

Main tool / activity. A recommendation about the main tool or activity to be used to develop the action corresponding to that touchpoint.

Resources. Other resources (tools, knowledge, documents, activities) that could be useful for this objective, complementing or enriching the main tool.

Participants. The list of stakeholders that should be engaged in each touchpoint. The catalogue of participants includes three main categories:

1. **Partners**. In some cases, differentiating those that are Living Lab Experts.
2. **Core team or host organisations**, which transition from potential host organisations to Host organisations along the development.
3. **Other local stakeholders**, which transition from invited stakeholders to potential stakeholders and finally participant stakeholders along the development.

#	Time (week #)	Touchpoint	Main tool / activity
1	-10	Introductory Sessions about Living Labs for partners	Online training
2	- 5-9	Mapping relevant problems and territories / communities / economic activities	Exploration of opportunities to apply the Living Lab framework in European regions
3	- 1-4	Negotiation with potential host organisations and core teams (persons and institutions)	Dialogue and negotiation
4	0	Definition of Canvas (Desirability): 3, 4	Co-creation workshop
5	1-4	Challenge mapping and preliminary prioritisation	Desk research / User research (interviews, focus groups) / Exploratory workshops
6	5	Stakeholder mapping	Exploratory workshop
7	5	Stakeholder classification and strategy for engagement	Co-creation workshop
8	6	Definition of Canvas (Desirability): 1, 2	Co-creation workshop
9	1-7	Introductory sessions about Living Labs and FARCLIMATE Project for stakeholders	Online training
10	8	Stakeholder integration in the Living Lab project for a specific case study	Co-creation workshop
11	9	Definition of Canvas (Feasibility): 5-9	Co-creation workshop
12	10-11	Challenge prioritisation and selection	Co-creation workshop
13	12-13	Definition of Canvas (Feasibility): 10 Strategy, 11 SWOT	Co-creation workshop
14	14	Evaluation of cycle 1	Living Lab Evaluation Framework
15	8-15	Living Lab Crash Course	Online training
16	16-17	Co-creation of prototypes and experiments	Ideation Workshop + Co-creation workshop
17	18	Definition of Canvas (Viability): 12, 13, 14	Co-creation workshop
18	19-23	Design of prototypes	Prototyping workshops
19	24-36	Pilot interventions	Pilot projects / Demonstrations / Experiments / Field trials
20	37	Evaluate the performance of prototypes	Data collection and analysis
21	38	Evaluation of cycle 2	Living Lab Evaluation Framework
Iterate activities 16 to 20 in successive cycles			
		Evaluation of successive cycles of interaction	
		IMPLEMENT: Demonstrate the system	
		SCALE UP: Exploit the solution	

Figure 8. Detailed view of the Case Study Journey. Each touchpoint is mapped with a colour code with respect to the phases of the integrative and complementary processes (see Fig. 7).

DESCRIPTION OF TOUCHPOINTS

A brief description of each touchpoint is provided, outlining the actions, participants, objectives, main tools, and expected results. Touchpoints are ordered according to the sequence suggested in the journey.

1. Introductory Sessions about Living Labs for partners

Short online training sessions conducted by experts to help project partners familiarise themselves with the living lab framework and tools.

2. Mapping relevant problems and territories / communities / economic activities

Exploration by partners of opportunities to apply the Living Lab framework in European regions using primary and secondary information, data and expert knowledge from partners and contacts. Prioritisation of these opportunities to select candidate case studies and potential host organisations.

3. Negotiation with potential host organisations and core teams (individuals and institutions)

Communication and negotiation between partners and potential host organisations to present the project, invite them to participate as case studies and negotiate the conditions of their participation.

4. Definition of Canvas (Desirability): 3 and 4

Co-creation workshop to define the first two desirability components (Living Lab context and host organisations) of the Living Lab Mapping Canvas by partners, incipient host organisation(s) and other invited stakeholders (potential participants in the future Living Lab).

5. Challenge mapping and preliminary prioritisation

Mapping of challenges related to climate adaptation relevant to the territory and community using a combination of desk research, user research (interviews and focus groups) and exploratory workshops by partners, the host organisation and other invited stakeholders. Prioritisation of challenges based on their relevance and the feasibility of solutions within the Living Lab format to select those that will be the focus of the case study.

6. Stakeholder mapping

Exploratory workshop to map relevant stakeholders for the selected challenges using the quadruple helix mapping framework and brainstorming tools, with the participation of partners, host organisation(s) and other invited stakeholders. See Annex 3 for more details and recommendations on stakeholder mapping.

7. Stakeholder classification and strategy for engagement

Co-creation workshop to analyse the stakeholder maps and classify stakeholders using a combination of tools (such as the power-interest matrix, the salience model and the attitude and knowledge stakeholder map) by partners, host organisation(s) and other invited stakeholders. The classification will allow us to define the strategy for engagement of the selected stakeholders in the same workshop. See Annex 3 for more details and recommendations about stakeholder analysis.

8. Definition of Canvas (Desirability): 1 and 2

Co-creation workshop to define the last two desirability components (purpose and vision, and scope) of the Living Lab Mapping Canvas with partners, incipient host organisation(s) and other invited stakeholders.

9. Introductory sessions on Living Labs and the FARCLIMATE Project for stakeholders

Online training carried out by experts to help host organisation(s) and potential stakeholders to immerse in the FARCLIMATE Project, the Living Lab framework and tools, and the case study corresponding to their territory and community.

10. Stakeholder integration in the Living Lab project for a specific case study

Co-creation workshop led by host organisation(s), with the support of partners, where potential stakeholders are invited. In this workshop, previous mappings of stakeholders and challenges are shared and revised to incorporate stakeholders' inputs and feedback. An agreement is reached regarding stakeholder participation, objectives of the case study, and the main next steps.

11. Definition of Canvas (Feasibility): 5-9

Co-creation workshop to define the first five feasibility components (5. Overview of all stakeholders, 6. Stakeholders and external roles, 7. People and internal roles, 8. Communication strategy & Channels, 9. Monitoring & Evaluation) of the Living Lab Mapping Canvas with host organisation(s) and participant stakeholders.

12. Challenge prioritisation and selection

Co-creation workshop by host organisation(s) and stakeholders to revise and improve the challenges identified for their territory and community, prioritise them and select those that will be addressed as part of the case study in a Living Lab format.

13. Definition of Canvas (Feasibility): 10 Strategy, 11 SWOT

Co-creation workshop to define the last two feasibility components (10 Strategy, 11 SWOT) of the Living Lab Mapping Canvas with host organisation(s) and stakeholders, using the 5 bold steps and other relevant tools.

14. Evaluation of cycle 1

After completing the first cycle of setup and deployment of the Living Lab (comprising touchpoints 1 to 13) its performance (process and results obtained) will be assessed by host organisation(s) and stakeholders with the support of partners using the Living Lab Evaluation Framework developed by ENoLL. This touchpoint implies the compilation of documentation and indicators and analysis of the information gathered and combines asynchronous activities and dialogue and discussion sessions.

15. Living Lab Crash Course

Online course covering Living Lab fundamentals, processes and tools to train participant stakeholders and other interested parties.

16. Co-creation of prototypes and experiments.

A series of ideation and co-creation workshops carried out by host organisation(s) and stakeholders to ideate, conceptualise and select the prototypes identified as potential solutions to the challenges. These workshops will also define the experiments that will be carried out with the prototypes to validate and improve them. Several tools for ideation, conceptualization and communication of ideas and design and planning of experiments are available.

17. Definition of Canvas (Viability): 12, 13, 14

Co-creation workshop to define the viability components (12. Governance, 13. Value for stakeholders, 14. Resources & Sustainability) of the Living Lab Mapping Canvas with host organisation(s) and stakeholders.

18. Design of prototypes

A series of prototyping workshops to design and build the prototypes selected previously, carried out by host organisation(s) and stakeholders, with support from technical experts if needed. The nature of the process and workshops will depend on the technical characteristics of the prototype, which could vary greatly (e.g., digital platforms, hardware, pilot installation, new business model, new organisational forms, or, in general, an intervention not requiring any technological development).

19. Pilot interventions

The built prototypes will be tested according to the experimental designs and plans defined previously. The experimental interventions could adopt a variety of formats including pilot projects, demonstrations, experiments or field trials, depending on the nature of the solution. These interventions will be carried out by host organisation(s) and stakeholders.

20. Evaluate the performance of prototypes

The data generated during the pilot interventions will be collected and analysed by host organisation(s) and stakeholders to assess the results of the experiments and evaluate the performance of the prototypes and solutions. Evidence and learnings obtained will allow us to iterate prototypes along cycles of experimentation until it is considered that the solution is ready for implementation and scale up.

21. Evaluation of cycle 2

After completing the second cycle of development of the Living Lab (comprising touchpoints 14 to 20) its performance (process and results obtained) will be assessed by host organisation(s) and stakeholders with the support of partners using the Living Lab Evaluation Framework developed by ENoLL. This touchpoint implies the compilation of documentation and indicators and analysis of the information gathered and combines asynchronous activities, dialogue and discussion sessions.

Following the completion of the second cycle, additional cycles may be developed to iterate activities 16 to 20 (improving prototypes and testing them with new experiments and interventions). Once a robust and effective solution is attained, the final two activities should be carried out, which will be greatly dependent on the nature of the solution:

IMPLEMENT: Demonstrate the system

SCALE UP: Exploit the solution

7 General Journey for Setting Up Living Labs Case Studies

While the stakeholder management strategy is designed to support the entire lifecycle of the case studies, this **initial version** -crafted **before the setup and implementation of the first batch of FARCLIMATE case studies**- places special **emphasis** on **setting up** the Living Labs. It's crucial to nail down the early stages of the journey to ensure successful initial engagement and **build a solid foundation of consensus** around the **challenges, objectives, and methods**. Once these foundational goals are met (addressing the problem space and the initial stages of the solution space in the integrative process), each case study and Living Lab will follow its own tailored plan and process, as the problems and contexts vary significantly across case studies (relating to the later stages of the solution space and deployment space).

It is important to remember that, despite the diversity of Living Labs, they all share common building blocks, as stated in the information provided to potential interested parties:

- A living lab is defined by its participants. Stakeholder engagement and participation are essential for successful living labs.

- A clear strategy from the beginning. Well-defined governance and business models for the living lab are crucial for stakeholder engagement and coordination.

- A core team for running the living lab, mainly from the organisation leading the living lab or other close collaborators. This team carries out the tasks for leading the living lab, such as management or coordination with stakeholders. As the case study progresses, the team will evolve with other roles such as the human interaction coordinator and project managers.

The setup should ensure the achievement of these building blocks, and to this end, the journey for establishing a Living Lab in each territory and case study should include the following general **sequence of phases** (see Fig. 9):

Figure 9. Flow Diagram of the Case Study Journey for setting up Living Labs in each territory / case study.

1. Initial mapping of relevant problems and territories

This activity was initially conducted in Task 2.2, with methods and results detailed in D2.2. FARCLIMATE partners undertook an exercise at the European scale to identify territories relevant to the project's scope, where fisheries, agriculture, and/or forestry are economically and socially significant, and where the impact of climate change is critical. The result of this exercise is a map of problems / communities / territories candidates to be case studies and future Living Labs. A prioritisation is established to identify those potential case studies where to explore the feasibility of the proposal and negotiations with local stakeholders will be initiated. Although this activity precedes the setup of case studies in strict terms, it is important to mention it to fully understand the complete journey.

2. Identification and negotiation with core teams (institutions and persons)

Based on expert knowledge and partner networks, a series of contacts and conversations are conducted in each potential case study to:

- **Validate** the **pertinence** of the proposal, (including the challenge's significance and the existence of local capabilities),.
- **Identify** the **key stakeholders** that could lead Living Labs, conforming the core team (identifying both institutions and persons).
- **Open communication channels** (formal and informal) to share the FARCLIMATE project, the format of case studies and Living Labs and the benefits of participating in the potential core team. Through this dialogue, local stakeholders' interest will be generated and validated, leading to negotiations to reach specific agreements for formalising the case study and starting the collaboration.

3.1 Mapping of stakeholders

During phase 1, a general mapping of challenges related to economic activities in the territories was created. After confirming the case studies, this exercise must be refined and focused on the territory, involving local stakeholders and ideally led by the core team (with support from project partners). The primary objective of this mapping is to develop a comprehensive map of relevant stakeholders that expands on the preliminary one, which only identified candidates for the core team. Annex 3 provides tools and recommendations for stakeholder mapping.

3.2 Mapping of specific problems / challenges

The second objective of the mapping is to identify the problems that should be strategically addressed by the living labs. The strategic relevance of these challenges is related to their global and local importance, their characteristics, and the presence of local capabilities. By “characteristics” we refer to the attributes of the problem that make it suitable for a participatory innovation approach.

Both activities, 3.1 and 3.2, occur in parallel and in most cases the same actions allow for progress on both objectives (e.g., a workshop where some potential stakeholders are invited and, through a creative process, both other stakeholders and the problems are identified).

For the identification and collection of local challenges, a combination of tools and approaches is suggested:

- **Gathering input** from stakeholders through surveys, interviews, workshops, and community meetings
- **Assessing the region or community** based on primary and secondary information and data to identify strengths and weaknesses as well as key challenges and opportunities

The identification of local challenges is a critical step in clearly defining the objectives and scope of the Living Lab. The objectives of a Living Lab can be related to a specific sector (e.g. agriculture, fisheries, forestry) or to different focus areas/sectors such as climate neutrality or sustainability. This step is incorporated in the Mapping Canvas within the sections concerning the objectives, scope, and strategy.

After this double mapping exercise, two parallel actions should be accomplished to move from possibilities and opportunities (“maps”) to decisions.

4.1. Engagement of stakeholders

Using the stakeholder map (obtained in 3.1) a series of activities will be carried out to invite stakeholders to explore the proposal, engage in dialogues with core team and other stakeholders, influence and propose changes and adaptations to the initial plan, and participate in the selection of challenges. The ultimate objective is to involve the various stakeholders in the complete development of the case study.

4.2. Selection of challenges and definition of objectives

Starting from the challenges and problems map (obtained in 3.2), a series of activities will be carried out to review the map, reflect on the different problems and challenges, and deepen and refine the understanding about them. In this way, the challenges will be prioritised and some of them will be selected as the starting point for the next phases of the Living Lab.

5. Plans and Teams

With the challenges defined and the stakeholder ecosystem declared, a series of exercises will allow for the planning of the activities, resources and teams responsible for the next phases of the processes. This exercise will be updated approximately every 6 months according to the results obtained in each work cycle.

8 Toolbox for Stakeholder Engagement

To develop the different actions required for each touchpoint of the journey, a **collection of tools** is suggested here. The term “tool” is understood broadly and encompasses actual tools as well as guidelines, templates, methodologies, platforms, good practices, or other resources.

This catalogue aims to provide flexibility to those in charge, allowing them to select and adapt different tools to the specificities of the case study. In some cases, a tool may be applicable only to a specific phase of the integrative or complementary processes, while in other cases, tools are more versatile and can be used in different phases.

The toolbox is organised as a database with the following fields:

Tool. Description of the tool.

Category. Each tool is classified in one of the following functional categories:

Communication | Documentation | Evaluation | Experimentation | Mediation | Stakeholders | Strategy | Training | Workshops.

Objectives. Description of the objectives that can be accomplished using the tool.

Applicability. The toolbox specifies, for each tool, the phases of the integrative process or the complementary processes (Canvas, Training, Evaluation, Communication) where this tool could be applicable.

Comments and Resources. Additional details about the tool and recommendations of resources (paper, webpages) to understand the tool in detail and access guidelines and templates.

Figure 10 shows a screenshot of the **catalogue**, summarising the fields of **tool**, **category**, **objectives**, and the **phases of the integrative process** (applicability). Complementary processes where the tool could be applicable, as well as comments and resources, are included in the original spreadsheet table provided in **Annex 4**, along with the Case Study Journey views.

Tool	Category	Objectives	Integrative process phases
Diffusion and communication activities: newsletters, events, webpages, news	Communication	Generate awareness among local stakeholders about the project, the impact of climate change and the living lab	Empathise
Knowledge platforms and hubs	Communication	Online resources to access to knowledge, methods, tools and experiences	General
Awareness campaigns	Communication	Inform stakeholders and citizens about their climate adaptation challenges and potential solutions (including the Living Lab framework)	Empathise
Advocacy strategies	Communication	A process that aims to influence change, especially through Living Labs, at the scale of the territory included in a case study	Empathise
Documentation	Documentation	Codification of knowledge generated from activities and projects to facilitate transference, feedback, continuous improvement and generation of new knowledge	General
Living Lab Evaluation Framework	Evaluation	Evaluate Living Lab performance and governance using the framework defined by ENoLL	Implement
Data collection and analysis	Evaluation	Gathering and analysis of data from observations and experimental tests to evaluate performance	Test
Pilot projects	Experimentation	Assess feasibility, usability, and effectiveness of prototypes in real contexts	Test
Demonstrations	Experimentation	Assess feasibility, usability, and effectiveness of prototypes in real contexts	Test
Experiments	Experimentation	Assess feasibility, usability, and effectiveness of prototypes in real contexts	Test
Field trials	Experimentation	Assess feasibility, usability, and effectiveness of prototypes in real contexts	Test
Mediation	Mediation	To facilitate the interaction of diverse stakeholders engaging with a collective goal assuring inclusion (the diversity knowledges, experiences and sensibilities corresponding to participants are represented) and individual and collective wellbeing	General
Quadruple helix mapping / brainstorming	Stakeholders	Stakeholder analysis and mapping	Empathise
Power-interest matrix	Stakeholders	Stakeholder analysis and mapping	Empathise
Salience model	Stakeholders	Classification of stakeholders to identify the salient (important) stakeholders from the trivial ones	Empathise
Attitude and Knowledge Stakeholder Map	Stakeholders	Classification of stakeholders to identify how to manage them	Empathise
Semi-structured interviews	Stakeholders	User / Stakeholder research	Empathise
Consultation to stakeholders	Stakeholders	Request the opinion of stakeholders about specific ideas and proposals using a variety of methods (interviews, focus groups, questionnaires)	General
Citizen / Stakeholder surveys	Stakeholders	Gather feedback and opinions on specific issues related to climate change adaptation from citizens (including stakeholders)	General
Citizen assemblies	Stakeholders	A democratic process based in open dialogue that allows participants to co-develop solutions	General
Business Model Canvas	Strategy	Design the strategy and components of a project to assure its desirability, feasibility and viability	Scale up
Value Proposition Canvas	Strategy	Design the value proposition of a product or service based in an in depth knowledge of the user	Ideate
Online introductory sessions (for partners)	Training	Sessions introducing the Living Lab framework to the partners of the FARCLIMATE project	General
Online introductory sessions (for stakeholders of case studies)	Training	Sessions introducing the Living Lab framework to stakeholders participating in the case studies	General
Living Lab Crash Course	Training	Course to learn about Living Lab framework, uses and methods	General
Exploratory workshops	Workshops	Identification and collection of insights and ideas (i.e., local challenges or mapping stakeholders)	General
Ideation workshops	Workshops	Brainstorming ideas about solutions, prototypes and generation of frameworks for assessment and selection	Ideate
Co-creation workshops	Workshops	Build new knowledge proposals engaging diverse stakeholders (for different goals)	General
Prototyping workshops	Workshops	Design prototypes (artifacts, solutions, experiments, plans) to be tested	Prototype

Fig. 10. Screenshot summarising the toolbox for stakeholder engagement. See Annex 4 for more details.

Below, we present a **brief description** of the **main categories of tools**. For a deeper understanding of these tools, several guidelines and toolkits related to Living Labs and other participatory approaches to innovation are available. We particularly recommend the guidelines from the EU Climate Adaptation Mission (MIP4Adapt, 2023), Project URBANOME (2021), and Reed et al. (2009), as well as the toolkits published by ENOLL².

1. COMMUNICATION

Diffusion and communication activities: newsletters, events, webpages, news.

- Generate awareness among local stakeholders about the project, the impact of climate change and the Living Lab.
- Cross-fertilization of experiences between individual Living Labs to identify best practices and define harmonised and scalable procedures.

Knowledge platforms and hubs. Online resources to access knowledge, methods, tools, experiences and good practices.

Awareness campaigns. Inform stakeholders and citizens about their climate adaptation challenges and potential solutions (including the Living Lab framework)

Advocacy strategies. A process that aims to influence change, especially through Living Labs, at the scale of the territory included in a case study.

2. DOCUMENTATION

Codification of knowledge generated from activities and projects to facilitate transference, feedback, continuous improvement and the generation of new knowledge.

3. EVALUATION

Living Lab Evaluation Framework. Evaluate Living Lab performance and governance using the framework defined by ENOLL. Application in 6-month cycles.

Data collection and analysis. Gathering and analysis of data from observations and experimental tests to evaluate performance.

4. EXPERIMENTATION

Assess feasibility, usability, and effectiveness through pilot projects, demonstrations, experiments, or field trials

5. MEDIATION

Facilitate the interaction of diverse stakeholders engaging with a collective goal, ensuring inclusion (the diversity of knowledge, experiences and sensibilities corresponding to participants are represented) and individual and collective wellbeing.

6. STAKEHOLDERS

Stakeholder analysis and mapping, using the Quadruple Helix mapping / brainstorming for mapping and the Power-interest matrix, the Saliency model and the Attitude and Knowledge Stakeholder Map for analysis (see Annex 3 for more details and recommendations)

² <https://enoll.org/toolkits/>

Classification of stakeholders, using the Saliency model (to identify the salient (important) stakeholders from the trivial ones) and the Attitude and Knowledge Stakeholder Map (to identify how to manage them).

Semi-structured interviews for user research

Consultation to stakeholders. Request the opinion of stakeholders about specific ideas and proposals using a variety of methods (interviews, focus groups, questionnaires)

Citizen / Stakeholder surveys. Gather feedback and opinions on specific issues related to climate change adaptation from citizens (including stakeholders)

Citizen assemblies. A democratic process based in open dialogue that allows participants to co-develop solutions

Stakeholders' relationships, needs and expectations thorough Value Proposition Canvas (jobs to be done / gains / pains) and Mapping of stakeholder networks. See Annex for tools for Stakeholder Mapping, including recommendations for effective engagement.

7. STRATEGY

Living Lab Mapping Canvas. Considered here a meta-tool or complementary process and, in this sense, is not included as a tool but different tools are included to develop the different components of the Mapping Canvas.

Business Model Canvas. Design the strategy and components of a project to assure its desirability, feasibility and viability

Value Proposition Canvas. Design the value proposition of a product or service based in an in depth knowledge of the user

8. TRAINING

Online introductory sessions for partners. Sessions introducing the Living Lab framework to the partners of the FARCLIMATE project

Online introductory sessions for stakeholders of case studies. Sessions introducing the Living Lab framework to stakeholders participating in the case studies

Living Lab Crash Course. A course to learn about Living Lab framework, uses and methods

9. WORKSHOPS

Exploratory workshops. Identification and collection of insights and ideas (e.g, local challenges or mapping stakeholders). Identification and mapping challenges, sharing experiences, generating ideas for initiatives and projects. Co-creation of solutions and projects. Formats: in-person and digital; event format or organic / continuous process

Ideation workshops. Brainstorming ideas about solutions, prototypes and generation of frameworks for assessment and selection

Co-creation workshops. Build new knowledge proposals by engaging diverse stakeholders (for different goals)

Prototyping workshops. Designing prototypes (artefacts, solutions, experiments, plans) to be tested.

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Project URBANOME. D2.1. *Good Practice guidelines for setting up and managing Urban Living Labs*, 2021.
<https://www.urbanome.eu/wp-content/uploads/Deliverable-D2.1.pdf>

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Wenger, E. *Communities of practice: Learning as a social system*. Systems thinker, 1998. 9(5), 2-3. <https://thesystemsthinker.com/wp-content/uploads/pdfs/090501pk.pdf>

Annex 1. Key concepts and terminology for stakeholder management in climate adaptation

Activity

In the Case Study Journey context, activities are the main actions that configure each touchpoint.

Blueprint

A detailed plan for setting up, deploying, and operating a Living Lab. It proposes a series of activities needed to develop each case study in a Living Lab format.

Case study Journey

Timing and sequence of actions, that define touchpoints, and the connections and dependencies among them that configure the setup and development of a Living Lab.

Citizen Lab

Infrastructures (institutions, tools), to generate citizen innovation, a participatory approach based in the collaboration between “professional experts” and “experts in experience” without a priori hierarchy of knowledge or stakeholders.

Design thinking

A human-centred approach and methodological framework to problem solving and innovation. Originally applied by designers to the creation of new products and services, it has gained relevance in recent decades as a general approach to innovation. A design thinking process is composed of two cycles (sometimes known as “double diamond”) combining divergence (ideation) and convergence (decision making and focus). The first one is centred around understanding the problem or challenge building empathy with users. In the second one, potential solutions are tested and improved in an agile way using experimental prototypes.

Expert in experience

Those individuals and groups who have experienced first-hand, for example, a health condition, a specific disease, dispossession, a climate crisis, abuse of power, discrimination, etc., which means that they not only have a deep knowledge of the symptoms and consequences of the situation they suffer from, but they are also familiar with the daily challenges they face, the unmet needs and the barriers to treatment and care.

Living Lab

Living Labs are a typology of innovation labs that operate as intermediaries among citizens, academia, industry, and governmental bodies (the quadruple Helix Model) to create and operate open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments, employing a systematic user co-creation approach that integrates research and innovation methodologies and activities in communities, with a focus on placing citizens at the heart of the innovation process (ENoLL, 2010).

Participant

In the context of this project and its case studies, a participant is any stakeholder (person or organisation) that engages actively in the co-creation processes characterising the living lab activities.

Prototype

In general, a prototype is an early model or release of a product built to test a concept or process. In the context of innovation processes, a prototype is any artefact encapsulating the main hypothesis about the potential solution to a challenge that can be tested experimentally to generate evidence and allow continuous improvement. Usually, a prototype is a material artefact, but in innovation the concept can be expanded including digital artefacts or performances. For any artifact to be considered a prototype, it must be used in an experimental context.

Stakeholder

All parties (persons and formal and informal organisations) who will be affected by or will affect the project strategy.

Tool

In the context of the Case Study Journey, the term 'tool' is understood in a broad way and encompasses actual tools and guidelines, templates, methodologies, platforms, good practices or other resources. These tools are elements needed to effectively develop the actions required in each touchpoint.

Touchpoint

Actions where different stakeholders interact with a definite goal and produce some result (being a piece of knowledge or decision).

Wicked problem

A kind of complex problems that are difficult or impossible to solve since they cannot be fully formulated, are multi-causal and at the same time any solution is always partial since the conditions are changing and/or the same solution also involves negative impacts.

Annex 2. Resources for the Definition of the Stakeholder Management Strategy

A brief guide is provided here to navigate and use the bibliography and resources included in the document, organizing the references and relevant materials according to their thematic focus and content.

Innovation frameworks and the importance of diversity and participation

Landscape of innovation approaches

Leurs, B. Landscape of innovation approaches. NESTA, 2018. <https://www.nesta.org.uk/blog/landscape-of-innovation-approaches/>

Wicked problems and participatory approaches for innovation:

Conklin, J. Dialogue Mapping: Building Shared Understanding of Wicked Problems; Wiley: Chichester, England, 2006.

Sultana, F.; McAllister, T.; Katyaini, S.; Blackstock, M. D. How to Achieve Safe Water Access for All: Work with Local Communities. *Nature* 2024, 627 (8005), 732–734. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-024-00886-z>

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Communities of innovation understood as communities of practice:

Wenger, E. Communities of practice: Learning as a social system. *Systems thinker*, 1998. 9(5), 2-3. <https://thesystemsthinker.com/wp-content/uploads/pdfs/090501pk.pdf>

General methodology of Living Labs

Introduction and general description

Bódi, Z.; De Los Ríos, M.; Enríquez, L. Living Lab Methodology and Online Handbook. Project REWAISE, 2022. https://rewaise.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/REWAISE-LL-online_handbook.pdf

ENoLL. (2010). Introducing ENoLL and its Living Lab community. <https://enoll.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/introducing-enoll-and-its-living-lab-community.pdf>

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Project URBANOME. D2.1. Good Practice guidelines for setting up and managing Urban Living Labs, 2021.
<https://www.urbanome.eu/wp-content/uploads/Deliverable-D2.1.pdf>

Living Lab Integrative Process

Mastelic, J. Stakeholders' engagement in the co-design of energy conservation interventions: The case of the Energy Living Lab, Doctoral Thesis, University of Lausanne. Doctoral Thesis, University of Lausanne, 2019.
https://sweet-lantern.ch/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/Mastelic_2019_The_Case_of_the_Energy_Living_Lab.pdf

Other frameworks for participatory innovation

Design

Kelley, T.; Kelley, D. Creative Confidence: Unleashing the Creative Potential Within Us All. Crown, 2013, 304 p.
<https://www.creativeconfidence.com/>

Lewrick, M.; Leifer, L.; Link, P. The Design Thinking Toolbox: A Guide to Mastering the Most Popular and Valuable Innovation Methods. Wiley, 2020, 320 p.

Stickdorn, M.; Hormess, M.E.; Lawrence, A.; Schneider, J. This Is Service Design Doing. A Practitioner's Handbook. O'Reilly Media, Inc., 2018, 568 p. <https://www.thisisservicedesigndoing.com/>

Citizen Labs

Gómez-Abad, D.; Freire, J. La Emergencia de Los Laboratorios Ciudadanos: Un Modelo Para La Creación de Comunidades de Innovación. European Public & Social Innovation Review 2023, 8 (2), 65–79.
<https://doi.org/10.31637/epsir-2023-248>

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https://doi.org/10.26754/ojs_ried/ijds.437

User Innovation

Gambardella, A.; Raasch, C.; von Hippel, E. The User Innovation Paradigm: Impacts on Markets and Welfare. Management Science 2017, 63 (5), 1450–1468. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.2015.2393>

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Von Hippel, E. Free Innovation; The MIT Press, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/9382.001.0001>

About Tools

Overview of methods

MIP4Adapt. Stakeholder and Citizen Engagement in Climate Adaptation: A DIY Manual. Version 1. September 2023. <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/mission/solutions/citizen-engagement-manual>

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Reed, M. S.; Graves, A.; Dandy, N.; Posthumus, H.; Hubacek, K.; Morris, J.; Prell, C.; Quinn, C. H.; Stringer, L. C. Who's in and Why? A Typology of Stakeholder Analysis Methods for Natural Resource Management. *Journal of Environmental Management* 2009, 90 (5), 1933–1949. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2009.01.001>

Stakeholder analysis and management

Geerdink, T.; Willems, R.; Botteman, M.; Schellekens, E.; Knapp, B.; Schwingenschloegl C. RESIN Actor Analysis for Urban Climate Adaptation. *Methods and Tools in support of Stakeholder Analysis and Involvement*, 2015. Ref. Ares(2015)4775375 - 02/11/2015. <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5a348f51e&appId=PPGMS>

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Tennakoon, M.; Kulatunga, U. *Stakeholder Management Models for Solid Waste Management Projects*; IEOM Society, 2021; Vol. 11. <https://doi.org/10.46254/AN11.20210547>

Interest-Power Matrix for Stakeholder mapping

Ackermann, F.; Eden, C. *Strategic Management of Stakeholders: Theory and Practice*. *Long Range Planning* 2011, 44 (3), 179–196. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2010.08.001>

Stakeholder Saliency Model

Kujala, J.; Lehtimäki, H.; Freeman, R.E.E. A Stakeholder Approach to Value Creation and Leadership. In: *Leading Change in a Complex World: Transdisciplinary Perspectives*. Tampere University Press, 2019, pp. 123-143

Mitchell, R. K.; Agle, B. R.; Wood, D. J. Toward a Theory of Stakeholder Identification and Saliency: Defining the Principle of Who and What Really Counts. *The Academy of Management Review* 1997, 22 (4), 853–886. <https://doi.org/10.2307/259247>

Attitude and Knowledge Stakeholder Map

Turner, R. (ed.). *Gower Handbook of Project Management*; Routledge, 2016.

Co-design Workshops

Project URBANOME. D2.1. Good Practice guidelines for setting up and managing Urban Living Labs, 2021.
<https://www.urbanome.eu/wp-content/uploads/Deliverable-D2.1.pdf>

Co-creation Journeys

Project SISCODE. *Toolbox for Co-creation Journeys*, 2019. <https://siscodeproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/toolkit-27092019-1.pdf>

Evaluation of Living Labs

Vervoort, K.; Trousse, B.; Desole, M.; Bamidis, P.; Konstantinidis, E.; Santonen, T.; Petsani, D.; Servais, D.; De Boer, D.; Spagnoli, F.; Onur, O.; Bertolin, J. Harmonizing the evaluation of living labs: a standardized evaluation framework. *Proceedings of the XXXIII ISPIM Innovation Conference "Innovating in a Digital World"*, Copenhagen, Denmark, 2022. LUT Scientific and Expertise Publications: ISBN 978-952-335-694-8. <http://www.theseus.fi/handle/10024/754099>

Documentation

Lafuente A.; Gómez-Abad, D.; Freire, J. El arte de documentar. En, Ciudadanía digital y democracia participativa. F Sierra, S Leetoy & T Gravante (eds.), Salamanca: Comunicación Social Ediciones y Publicaciones, 2018, pp. 47-59.

Repositories of tools, templates and guidelines for innovation, design thinking and service design

<https://www.designcouncil.org.uk/our-resources/framework-for-innovation/>

<https://www.thisisservicedesigndoing.com/methods>

<https://www.creativeconfidence.com/tools/>

<https://www.designkit.org/>

<https://www.boardofinnovation.com/tools/>

Annex 3. Tools and recommendations for stakeholder mapping and effective management

A robust and exhaustive mapping of relevant stakeholders related to each case study (linked to a territory and community) is essential to ensure that the diversity of interests, experiences, and knowledge are represented in each Living Lab. This representation is critical for the success of the process. In this annex, we first summarise the preliminary activities carried out in FARCLIMATE, and then present some observations and recommendations about methods for stakeholder analysis to guide the different mapping exercises that will be part of the development of the various case studies.

Preliminary mapping exercises in the FARCLIMATE project

Two exercises have been conducted in the preparation of the proposal and the project initiation, respectively, and they constitute the baseline for addressing the in-depth mapping of stakeholders for each case study:

1. A preliminary stakeholder analysis was carried out for the proposal of the project to identify and categorise key stakeholders of the FARCLIMATE project. The following categories were defined:

- **Responsible authorities:** Regional government policy makers; local government policy makers
- **Private sector:** industries and business (with main focus on SMEs), business associations and labour unions.
- **General public:** consumer and civil society organisations.
- **Science and innovation:** academia, research and technology centres.
- **NGOs.**
- **Professionals and experts** (Agriculture, Fishery, Forestry, Business Development)

2. A preliminary mapping exercise was conducted as part of a stakeholder engagement workshop, led by ENOLL, which took place online on February 26, 2024. The workshop's main objective was to engage in a collaborative brainstorming session focused on identifying quadruple helix stakeholders for the case studies. It was designed to deepen the FARCLIMATE partners' understanding of the Living Lab landscape within each regional area across the three distinct sectors (for a more detailed description, see **Section 3 of D2.1**).

This preliminary exercise did not differentiate between case studies (which were still being defined at that time), but separate exercises were carried out for three main activity categories: forestry, agriculture, and fisheries.

The session was structured around three main activities, with relevant introductory explanations and a subsequent sharing of the exercise results:

- **Brainstorming exercise** on stakeholders for the case studies, grouped according to the quadruple helix. Relevant stakeholders were mapped and added to a Miro board (Fig. 11).
- **Power vs. Interest exercise:** Application of the Power vs. Interest matrix in breakout rooms for Agriculture, Fisheries, and Forestry, using Miro (Fig 12).
- **Discussion on key stakeholders:** The exercise focused on identifying an outreach strategy for the “key players” located in the quadrant of high power and high interest (Fig. 13).

This workshop added more granularity to the analysis of the proposal and allowed partners to become familiar with the various tools provided for stakeholder analysis.

Fig. 11. Miro board for brainstorming exercise on stakeholders of the case studies, grouped along the quadruple helix. Source Adapted from the materials prepared by ENoLL for the stakeholder engagement workshop.

Fig. 12. Power vs. Interest matrix. Source: materials prepared by ENoLL for the stakeholder engagement workshop.

	How would you reach out to them?	How do we think they can contribute?	What expectations do they have for their participation?	What can we promise/ offer to them? What do they gain from their participation?
Key Player 1:				
Key Player 2:				
Key Player 3:				
Key Player 4:				
Key player 5:				

Fig. 13. Outreach strategy identification exercise. Source: materials prepared by ENoLL for the stakeholder engagement workshop.

Methods and recommendations for stakeholder analysis

The **DIY Manual for Stakeholder and Citizen Engagement in Climate Change Adaptation** (MIP4Adapt, 2023) offers an informative and educational introduction to stakeholder mapping and network analysis in “**Step 1: Preparing the Ground for Adaptation**”. It provides a concise overview of key aspects to consider, along with relevant references in the **Annex** of the document.

The **RESIN guide “Actor Analysis for Urban Climate Adaptation: Methods and Tools in Support of Stakeholder Analysis and Involvement”** (Geerdink et al., 2015) provides a comprehensive overview of **methods and tools** for identifying and engaging stakeholders in the various steps of preparing for and developing climate change adaptation strategies. This guide, notable for its clarity and methodological rigour, divides stakeholder analysis into three distinct steps, each with its own purpose:

1. **Identification of stakeholders** through stakeholder mapping
2. **Categorization of stakeholders** (e.g., using an influence-interest matrix)
3. **Analysis of the relationships** between stakeholders

A thorough stakeholder analysis encompasses all three steps. The guide details various tools and methods for each activity, each offering unique insights into stakeholders’ positions. The choice of method or tool depends on the **objectives**, **context** (complexity and uncertainty), available **time** and **budget**, and required **knowledge** and **skills**. With more time and resources, and the right expertise, a deeper understanding can be achieved. The guide concludes with practical advice for preparing and conducting stakeholder analysis activities.

Finally, methods for stakeholder analysis are also detailed in various **ENoLL resources and guidelines** produced from projects using the Living Lab framework (see Annex 2). Below is a brief overview of the three categorization methods selected by ENoLL for the introductory immersion during the previously mentioned stakeholder engagement workshop (these methods correspond to Group 2 in the RESIN guide). The Power vs. Interest matrix was the method applied during the workshop.

Power vs interest matrix

A popular approach in stakeholder analysis is the power-vs. interest matrix, which is categorised as a top-down or analytical method. This technique classifies stakeholders into four groups based on their relative power and interest, or their influence and relevance concerning the issue at hand (Ackermann & Eden, 2011). Using the power-interest matrix can help identify fringe stakeholders who may be overlooked due to their lesser control over and interest in the issue (Reed et al., 2009). Here, "**power**" refers to the stakeholders' ability to impact the matter being discussed, while "**interest**" encompasses both their positive and negative stakes in the topic (Tennakoon & Kulatunga, 2021). This matrix (see Fig 12) provides a clear view of how stakeholders' power and interest influence their role and impact in the discussion.

The power vs interest matrix for stakeholder identification provides some insights about channels and efforts of communication and engagement campaigns:

- Least important (low power / low interest). General communication channels like newsletters
- Show consideration (high power / low interest). Engage and consult with them, addressing their needs to motivate their involvement in the activities. Through studying their motivations, a better understanding of their needs and incentives for participation can be grasped.
- Meeting their needs (low power / high interest). They are likely to actively engage in user engagement activities and should be kept informed and invited to participate in engagement events.
- Key players (high power / high interest). Engaging with them regularly, consulting them, and involving them in decision-making processes are crucial for the success and sustainability of Living Lab activities.

Stakeholder Salience Model

The Salience model is a dynamic tool for distinguishing between key stakeholders and those of lesser importance (Kujala et al., 2019; Mitchell et al., 1997). This three-dimensional model evaluates stakeholders based on power, legitimacy, and urgency. The model is described by a Venn diagram where these three factors intersect (Fig 14):

- **Power** indicates a stakeholder's ability to influence the project.
- **Legitimacy** reflects the stakeholder's rightful involvement.
- **Urgency** measures how promptly the stakeholder's needs must be addressed.

Fig. 14. The Venn diagram of the Salience Model.

This intersection creates seven distinct categories of stakeholders, along with a category for those not considered stakeholders. The Venn diagram visually represents how power, legitimacy, and urgency overlap, offering a clear way to prioritise and engage with stakeholders effectively.

Attitude and Knowledge Stakeholder Map

This tool is a matrix designed to map stakeholders' understanding and attitudes toward the project (Turner, 2016). Rather than using a range, the matrix categorises stakeholders into specific boxes (Fig 15). Stakeholders who are both aware of and supportive of the initiative are considered "heroes" but should not be taken for granted. Supportive yet uninformed stakeholders need to be nurtured to ensure they remain engaged. Uninformed and dissenting stakeholders represent a crucial area for intervention, as their attitudes can be shifted. Stakeholders who are both opposed and aware may never become supportive, and it is important to develop contingency measures to manage the risks associated with these negative stakeholders.

Fig. 15. Attitude and knowledge stakeholder matrix.

Final remarks: paying attention and harnessing diversity

Managing diversity is crucial in open innovation processes, such as those within Living Labs (Santonen, 2016). As described in D2.1, while it's important to prioritise stakeholders with high power and high interest, it is also essential to develop strategies to engage stakeholders who are relevant but initially lack interest or the reputation and capabilities to actively participate in the Living Lab.

Managing stakeholder expectations is critical to the success of a participatory process. Pay attention to clearly describing "how much" will be required from them (e.g., the expected level of participation) and what they will receive in return.

And a final recommendation, which we consider key to the success of active stakeholder involvement: start with "**why**," and seek the **inspiration** that brings parties together. Everything starts with communication between people.

Annex 4. Blueprint Case Study Journey and Toolbox for Stakeholder management

The file containing the original spreadsheet tables of the high-level and detailed views of the Case Study Journey, as well as the Toolbox for Stakeholder management, is available [at this link](https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1dLNEorOgzBVuT8zDeHJuqQ7CM2ocaf-sPRX7WO5f7j2g/edit?usp=sharing):
<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1dLNEorOgzBVuT8zDeHJuqQ7CM2ocaf-sPRX7WO5f7j2g/edit?usp=sharing>

4.1. High-level Case Study Journey

4.2. Detailed Case Study Journey

4.3. Toolbox for stakeholder management

PROCESSES

		Problem space			Solution space			Deployment space	
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Living Lab Integrative Process		EMPATHISE: Select a practice	EMPATHISE: Integrate Stakeholders	DEFINE: Uncover barriers	CREATE:Co-design p	PROTOTYPE: Pilot an intervention	TEST: Evaluate performance	IMPLEMENT: Demonstrate the system	SCALE UP: Exploit the solution
Selection and activation of case studies	Mapping problems and territories	Negotiation with core teams							
Living Lab Mapping Canvas		Desirability 3, 4		Feasibility 1, 2		Viability 5, 6, 7, 8, 9			10, 11
Trainings		Introductory sessions (partners)	Introductory sessions (stakeholders)			Living Lab Crash Course			
Evaluation				Cycle 1		Cycle 2		Cycle 3	
Communication									
Time (months)		0-2	3-4	5-6	7-12		13-		
Duration (months)		2	2	2	<1	5	<1		

#	Time	Touchpoint	Main tool / activity	Resources	Participants
1	-10	Introductory Sessions about Living Labs for partners	Online training		Living Lab Experts + Partners
2	- 5-9	Mapping relevant problems and territories / communities /	Exploration of opportunities to apply	Primary and secondary information and	Partners
3	- 1-4	Negotiation with potential host organisations and core	Dialogue and negotiation	Documentation about the project	Partners + Potential host
4	0	Definition of Canvas (Desirability): 3, 4	Co-creation workshop	Living Lab Mapping Canvas	Partners + Host organisation(s)
5	1-4	Challenge mapping and preliminary prioritisation	Desk research / User research		Partners + Host organisation(s)
6	5	Stakeholder mapping	Exploratory workshop	Quadruple helix mapping / brainstorming	Partners + Host organisation(s)
7	5	Stakeholder classification and strategy for engagement	Co-creation workshop	Power-interest matrix / Salience model	Partners + Host organisation(s)
8	6	Definition of Canvas (Desirability): 1, 2	Co-creation workshop	Living Lab Mapping Canvas	Partners + Host organisation(s)
9	1-7	Introductory sessions on Living Labs and the FARCLIMATE	Online training		Living Lab Experts + Partners +
10	8	Stakeholder integration in the Living Lab project for a	Co-creation workshop		Partners + Host organisation(s)
11	9	Definition of Canvas (Feasibility): 5-9	Co-creation workshop	Living Lab Mapping Canvas	Host organisation(s) +
12	10-11	Challenge prioritisation and selection	Co-creation workshop		Host organisation(s) +
13	12-13	Definition of Canvas (Feasibility): 10 Strategy, 11 SWOT	Co-creation workshop	Living Lab Mapping Canvas / 5 bold	Host organisation(s) +
14	14	Evaluation of cycle 1	Living Lab Evaluation Framework		Host organisation(s) +
15	8-15	Living Lab Crash Course	Online training		Participant stakeholders
16	16-17	Co-creation of prototypes and experiments	Ideation Workshop + Co-creation	Brainstorming / Storyboards / Planning	Host organisation(s) +
17	18	Definition of Canvas (Viability): 12, 13, 14	Co-creation workshop	Living Lab Mapping Canvas	Host organisation(s) +
18	19-23	Design of prototypes	Prototyping workshops		Host organisation(s) +
19	24-36	Pilot interventions	Experiments / Field trials		Host organisation(s) +
20	37	Evaluate the performance of prototypes	Data collection and analysis		Host organisation(s) +
21	38	Evaluation of cycle 2	Living Lab Evaluation Framework		Host organisation(s) +
		Iterate activities 16 to 20 in successive cycles			
		Evaluation of successive cycles of interaction			
		IMPLEMENT: Demonstrate the system			
		SCALE UP: Exploit the solution			

Tool	Category	Objectives	Integrative process phases	Complementary processes				Comments and Resources
				Canvas	Training	Evaluation	Communication	
Diffusion and communication activities: newsletters, events, webpages, news	Communication	Generate awareness among local stakeholders about the project, the impact of climate change and the living lab	Empathise				X	Collaborating the core team (production of contents and diffusion) and partners (production of part of the contents) https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/mission/solutions/citizen-engagement-manual
Knowledge platforms and hubs	Communication	Online resources to access to knowledge, methods, tools and experiences	General		X			
Awareness campaigns	Communication	Inform stakeholders and citizens about their climate adaptation challenges and potential solutions (including the Living Lab framework)	Empathise				X	https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/mission/solutions/citizen-engagement-manual
Advocacy strategies	Communication	A process that aims to influence change, especially through Living Labs, at the scale of the territory included in a case study	Empathise				X	https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/mission/solutions/citizen-engagement-manual
Documentation	Documentation	Codification of knowledge generated from activities and projects to facilitate transference, feedback, continuous improvement and generation of new knowledge	General		X		X	General category that should be decomposed in a series of specific tools (web, reports, infographics and diagrams ...). Transversal tool usable in most of the activities. Lafuente et al. (2018) https://www.docart.app/
Living Lab Evaluation Framework	Evaluation	Evaluate Living Lab performance and governance using the framework defined by ENoLL	Implement				X	Complimentary tools: focus groups, questionnaires Vervoort et al. (2022)
Data collection and analysis	Evaluation	Gathering and analysis of data from observations and experimental tests to evaluate performance	Test				X	
Pilot projects	Experimentation	Assess feasibility, usability, and effectiveness of prototypes in real contexts	Test					See Annex 2. Repositories of tools for innovation, design thinking and service design
Demonstrations	Experimentation	Assess feasibility, usability, and effectiveness of prototypes in real contexts	Test					See Annex 2. Repositories of tools for innovation, design thinking and service design
Experiments	Experimentation	Assess feasibility, usability, and effectiveness of prototypes in real contexts	Test					See Annex 2. Repositories of tools for innovation, design thinking and service design
Field trials	Experimentation	Assess feasibility, usability, and effectiveness of prototypes in real contexts	Test					See Annex 2. Repositories of tools for innovation, design thinking and service design
Mediation	Mediation	To facilitate the interaction of diverse stakeholders engaging with a collective goal assuring inclusion (the diversity knowledges, experiences and sensibilities corresponding to participants are represented) and individual and collective wellbeing	General		X		X	General category that should be decomposed in a series of specific tools. Transversal tool usable in most of collective activities.
Quadruple helix mapping / brainstorming	Stakeholders	Stakeholder analysis and mapping	Empathise	5, 6				See Annex 3
Power-interest matrix	Stakeholders	Stakeholder analysis and mapping	Empathise	5, 6				Ackermann & Eden (2011). See Annex 3
Salience model	Stakeholders	Classification of stakeholders to identify the salient (important) stakeholders from the trivial ones	Empathise	6				Kujala et al. (2019); Mitchell et al. (1997). See Annex 3
Attitude and Knowledge Stakeholder Map	Stakeholders	Classification of stakeholders to identify how to manage them	Empathise	5, 6				Turner (2016)
Semi-structured interviews	Stakeholders	User / Stakeholder research	Empathise	1, 2, 3, 5, 6				
Consultation to stakeholders	Stakeholders	Request the opinion of stakeholders about specific ideas and proposals using a variety of methods (interviews, focus groups, questionnaires)	General				X	https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/mission/solutions/citizen-engagement-manual
Citizen / Stakeholder surveys	Stakeholders	Gather feedback and opinions on specific issues related to climate change adaptation from citizens (including stakeholders)	General				X	https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/mission/solutions/citizen-engagement-manual
Citizen assemblies	Stakeholders	A democratic process based in open dialogue that allows participants to co-develop solutions	General				X	https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/mission/solutions/citizen-engagement-manual
Business Model Canvas	Strategy	Design the strategy and components of a project to assure its desirability, feasibility and viability	Scale up	14				https://www.strategyzer.com/library/the-business-model-canvas
Value Proposition Canvas	Strategy	Design the value proposition of a product or service based in an in depth knowledge of the user	Ideate					https://www.strategyzer.com/library/the-value-proposition-canvas
Online introductory sessions (for partners)	Training	Sessions introducing the Living Lab framework to the partners of the FARCLIMATE project	General			X		
Online introductory sessions (for stakeholders of case studies)	Training	Sessions introducing the Living Lab framework to stakeholders participating in the case studies	General			X		
Living Lab Crash Course	Training	Course to learn about Living Lab framework, uses and methods	General			X		There are derived tools focused in specific types of projects (platform canvas, lean canvas ...)
Exploratory workshops	Workshops	Identification and collection of insights and ideas (i.e., local challenges or mapping stakeholders)	General					See Annex 2. Repositories of tools for innovation, design thinking and service design
Ideation workshops	Workshops	Brainstorming ideas about solutions, prototypes and generation of frameworks for assessment and selection	Ideate					See Annex 2. Repositories of tools for innovation, design thinking and service design
Co-creation workshops	Workshops	Build new knowledge proposals engaging diverse stakeholders (for different goals)	General	1-14				See Annex 2. Repositories of tools for innovation, design thinking and service design
Prototyping workshops	Workshops	Design prototypes (artifacts, solutions, experiments, plans) to be tested	Prototype					See Annex 2. Repositories of tools for innovation, design thinking and service design